

Effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non Stress Test on selected physiological parameters of fetus and mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Pregnancy is considered as normal biological event. 6-33% of pregnant women experience pregnancy complications related to mother and fetus or both. Pregnant women should receive appropriate antenatal care (ANC) to promote maternal, fetal health. According to World Health Organization (WHO) (2021), Antenatal Care is essential for protecting the health of women and their unborn fetus. Health care professionals should ensure the better health status for mothers and their fetus and also to detect any abnormality. During ante partum period, several tests are performed routinely to monitor fetal well being in that the most commonly recognized screening measure of fetal well being is the measurement of the fetal heart rate rhythm with electronic fetal monitoring. Non stress test (NST) is frequently used as first choice for fetal health and survival assessment.

According to American Pregnancy Association (2021) Non stress Test is a simple, non-invasive, Inexpensive test performed in pregnancies over 28 weeks gestation for ante partum fetal surveillance. It is easy to perform and causes no inconvenience or complications to the mother.

A variety positions can be used during Non stress test such as Semi fowler's, Supine, Left lateral and maternal positioning may affect the physiological health of the mother and fetus as well as psychological well being of mother also.

Objectives:

To assess the effectiveness of different maternal positions during NST on selected physiological parameters of fetus and mothers admitted in Antenatal ward of selected hospitals.

Methods:

A quantitative, Quasi-experimental one group counterbalanced repeated measure research design was adopted. The study was conducted among 60 antenatal mothers selected using non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured demographic proforma, Self Prepared Parameter Sheet and Modified Discomfort Scale. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics including Chi-square test and ANOVA test were used for comparison and association analysis.

Results:

The demographic findings indicated that the majority of mothers were aged 21–30 years (68.33%), followed by below 20 years (16.67%) and above 30 years (15%). Most participants belonged to the middle socioeconomic group (53.33% with income ₹20,000–40,000), while 40% had income between ₹40,000–50,000. A higher proportion of mothers were not working (60%), with 21.67% employed and 18.33% students. Educational status showed that most mothers had completed 12th standard (63.33%), followed by graduates (28.33%). More than half resided in urban areas (58.33%). Regarding obstetrical score, 50% were primigravida, and most mothers had completed third or fourth antenatal visits (86.66%).

Pre-test physiological parameters (systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, oxygen saturation, and respiratory rate) showed no significant differences across supine, left lateral, and semi-Fowler's positions ($p>0.05$). Similarly, during the test, systolic and diastolic blood pressure remained statistically non-significant across positions ($p>0.05$). However, significant differences were observed in heart rate ($F=3.88$, $p=0.02$), oxygen saturation ($F=5.68$, $p=0.004$), and respiratory rate ($F=3.29$, $p=0.04$) during the test.

Regarding discomfort levels before the test, most mothers experienced moderate discomfort in the supine position (63.33%), while mild discomfort was more common in left lateral (61.67%) and semi-Fowler's positions (61.67%). During the test, left lateral position showed better comfort with 38.33% reporting no discomfort, compared to 10% in supine and 8.33% in semi-Fowler's position.

Comparison of discomfort levels across positions revealed a statistically significant difference ($F=23.25$, $p<0.001$), with the lowest discomfort in supine position (mean=1.25), followed by left lateral (mean=2.06) and highest in semi-Fowler's position (mean=2.80). Similarly, fetal heart rate differed significantly across positions ($F=27.72$, $p<0.001$), with highest mean in supine position (152.97 bpm), followed by semi-Fowler's (151.63 bpm) and lowest in left lateral position (147.23 bpm).

Association analysis showed that in the supine position, discomfort levels were significantly associated with age and obstetrical score ($p<0.05$), whereas in the left lateral position, significant association was found with age and occupation ($p<0.05$). No significant associations were observed between discomfort levels and demographic variables in semi-Fowler's position ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion:

The study concludes that left lateral position is the most effective maternal position during NST, as it improves maternal comfort and promotes optimal fetal heart rate, making it a simple, safe and cost effective nursing intervention in antenatal care.

Keywords: Different maternal positions, Non Stress Test, Antenatal mothers, Discomfort Scale, demographic variables.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is considered as normal biological event. 6-33% of pregnant women experience pregnancy complications related to mother and fetus or both. Pregnant women should receive appropriate antenatal care (ANC) to promote maternal, fetal health. According to World Health Organization (WHO) (2021), Antenatal Care is essential for protecting the health of women and their unborn fetus. Health care professionals should ensure the better health status for mothers and their fetus and also to detect any abnormality. During ante partum period, several tests are performed routinely to monitor fetal well-being in that the most commonly recognized screening measure of fetal well-being is the measurement of the fetal heart rate rhythm with electronic fetal monitoring. Non stress test (NST) is frequently used as first choice for fetal health and survival assessment.

According to American Pregnancy Association (2021) Non stress Test is a simple, non-invasive, Inexpensive test performed in pregnancies over 28 weeks gestation for ante partum fetal surveillance. It is easy to perform and causes no inconvenience or complications to the mother. A variety of positions can be used during Non stress test such as Semi Fowler's, Supine, left lateral and maternal positioning may affect the physiological health of the mother and fetus as well as psychological well-being of mother also.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Maternal and fetal health monitoring is a key priority during pregnancy to ensure positive outcomes for both mother and baby. Among the various tools used to monitor fetal well-being, the Non Stress Test (NST) holds a crucial place due to its non-invasive nature and ability to detect fetal health in real time. The NST (Non Stress Test) is commonly performed in antenatal outpatient departments as well as inpatient departments to assess the relationship between fetal heart rate (FHR) and fetal movements, providing an indirect measure of fetal oxygenation and autonomic nervous system function. The importance of Non stress test in Antenatal care The NST is particularly valuable in high risk pregnancies, where fetal well-being may be compromised due to maternal or fetal complications such as hypertensive disorders, gestational diabetes, intrauterine growth restriction, post-term pregnancies.

The test evaluates the ability of the placenta to provide adequate oxygenation and nutrients to the fetus by monitoring the accelerations of the fetal heart rate in response to fetal movements. The accuracy of Non stress Test results can be influenced by maternal and fetal factors, one of which is maternal positioning during the test. The position of mother assumes during the Non Stress Test has profound effects on her cardiovascular system, uteroplacental circulation and fetal oxygenation. The gravid uterus, particularly in the third trimester, can compress the inferior vena cava and abdominal aorta, significantly altering maternal hemodynamic and placental blood flow. These changes can impact both maternal and fetal parameters observed during the test. Significance of maternal comfort is another important aspect of Non stress Test. The test requires the mother to remain in a specific position for an extended period (often 20-40 minutes) which can cause discomfort. Discomfort during the test can elevate maternal stress levels, leading to physiological changes such as increased heart rate or blood pressure. These changes can indirectly influence fetal heart rate potentially affecting the accuracy of the Non Stress Test.

Evaluation of ante partum fetal condition has become essential to obstetric care in both normal and complicated pregnancies. Fetal distress is the condition in which fetal physiology is altered due to hypoxia so as to lead to death or permanent neurological injury. It is a progressive condition, and if not corrected will result in damage to central nervous system or death. There are so many biochemical and biophysical assessment methods that have been introduced during the past two decades. Few of the tests are based on fetal heart rate monitoring which plays an important role in management of women who are pregnant. Advances in perinatal care have resulted dramatic decrease of perinatal mortality. These advances include introduction of electronic fetal monitoring, ultrasound, computerized fetal assessment and so on. Continuous electronic fetal monitoring is currently the principal screening method for the diagnosis of fetal distress.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The Non Stress Test is one of the most common used tools to assess fetal well being , particularly in high risk pregnancies. This non – invasive methods evaluate the fetal heart rate responses to spontaneous fetal movements , which is an indicator of adequate oxygenation and a autonomic nervous system . However the effectiveness and realibility of the NST depend on multiple factor, including the maternal position during the test Challenges associated with maternal positioning physiological effects on maternal circulation , during the late pregnancy the weight of the gravid uterus can compress major blood vessels such as inferior vena cava and aorta. This can lead to supine hypotensive syndrome characterized by a drop in maternal blood pressure, dizziness and reduced blood flow to the placenta, thereby impacting fetal oxygenation different maternal positions influence parameters such as: Maternal heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygenation levels, Fetal heart rate patterns, variability, and reactivity is essential for ensuring the accuracy of NST results and the comfort of the mother during the test. The need for this study becomes even more critical in high-risk pregnancies, such as those involving: gestational diabetes, pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH),intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR),multiple gestations. Despite the relevance of maternal positioning, there is a lack of comprehensive studies exploring its impact on both maternal and fetal physical and physiological parameters during NST.

This study is critical as it seeks to bridge this gap in knowledge by investigating the influence of specific maternal positions on parameters such as maternal blood pressure, pulse rate, and fetal heart rate patterns. It aims to provide evidence that can support the development of standardized guidelines for maternal positioning during NST, ultimately enhancing the quality of antenatal care. Effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non Stress Test on selected physiological parameters of fetus and mothers.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a Quasi-experimental one group counterbalanced repeated to assess Effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non Stress Test on selected physiological parameters of fetus and mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals.The study was conducted in the labour ward of a selected hospital over a period of 28 days. The target population included antenatal mothers admitted in selected

hospitals. A total sample of 60 antenatal mothers was selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a selected demographic variable, Self Prepared Parameter Sheet and Modified Discomfort Scale. The tool was validated by experts and reliability was established prior to the study. A pilot study was conducted to assess feasibility. Ethical approval was obtained and informed consent was taken from participants before data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics

RESULT

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

SECTION – I Description of samples (Antenatal mother) based on their demographic data in terms of frequency and percentage

1.Age- According to age of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 16.67% of them were from age group below 20 years of age, 68.33% from 21-30 years and 15% of mothers of age above 30 years.

2.Socio economic status -In this study, according to socioeconomic status of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 40% of them had income in Rs 40000 - 50000, 53.33% answered Rs 20000 - 40000 and 6.67% of mothers answered as < Rs 20000.

3.Occupation - According to occupation of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 21.67% of them were working, 60% answered as not working, 18.33% of them were students and no one of them from other occupation.

4.Education - In this study, according to education of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 8.33% of them educated up to 10th standard, 63.33% educated up to 12th standard, 28.33% of mothers were graduates and no one were post-graduate.

5.Area of residence - According to area of residence of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 58.33% of them were from urban area, 33.33% from rural residential area and 8.33% of mother from slum residence.

6.Obstetrical score - According to obstetrical score of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, 50% of them with score Gravida 1, 36.67% mothers with score Gravida 2 and 13.33% of mothers with score Gravida 3.

7.Antenatal visit- According to antenatal visit of mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals, no one of them answered as one, 13.33% had second visit, 43.33% answered as third visit and 43.33% of them answered as fourth visit.

Section II

Deals with analysis of data related to assessment of the physiological parameters of fetus and mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals.

Table 1: General assessments of the physiological parameters of fetus and mothers**n=60**

Physiological parameters	Supine		Left Lateral		Semi-Fowler's		F value	p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Before Test								
SBP	122.30	10.11	122.58	8.00	124.05	7.32	0.72	0.48
DBP	77.61	9.95	79.23	7.48	78.96	7.03	0.66	0.51
Heart rate	86.60	4.43	85.66	4.26	85.40	3.86	1.35	0.26
Oxygen saturation	97.68	0.94	97.76	0.98	97.68	1.00	0.15	0.86
Respiratory rate	21.10	1.06	21.10	1.06	20.76	1.22	1.76	0.17
During Test								
SBP	121.42	6.83	120.92	5.32	121.65	5.52	0.24	0.78
DBP	80.06	5.24	79.43	4.86	80.36	5.08	0.53	0.58
Heart rate	81.13	4.40	80.00	4.03	79.10	3.52	3.88	0.02
Oxygen saturation	98.58	0.96	99.10	0.89	98.65	0.88	5.68	0.004
Respiratory rate	19.36	1.05	18.85	1.14	19.15	1.11	3.29	0.040

Table 2: General assessments of Level of Discomfort – Before test**n=60**

Before Test							
Level of Discomfort	Positions	Supine		Left Lateral		Semi-Fowler's	
	Score	F	%	F	%	F	%
REFERENCES	0	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Mild	1-3	18	30.00	37	61.67	37	61.67
Moderate	4-6	38	63.33	23	38.33	22	36.67
Severe	7-9	4	6.67	0	0.00	1	1.67
Extreme	10	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00

Table 3: General assessments of Level of Discomfort – During test**n=60**

During Test							
Level of Discomfort	Positions	Supine		Left Lateral		Semi-Fowler's	
	Score	F	%	F	%	F	%
No discomfort	0	6	10.00	23	38.33	5	8.33
Mild	1-3	36	60.00	35	58.33	50	83.33
Moderate	4-6	18	30.00	2	3.33	5	8.33
Severe	7-9	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Extreme	10	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00

SECTION III

- ❖ Deals with analysis of data related to effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test on discomfort levels mothers admitted in antenatal ward of hospitals.

Table 4: Comparison of discomfort levels in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test**n=60**

DISCOMFORT - During Test						
Positions	N	Mean	SD	F value	p value	
Supine	60	1.25	1.15	23.25	0.000	
Left Lateral	60	2.06	1.08			
Semi-Fowler's	60	2.80	1.45			

Figure 1: Comparison of discomfort levels in different maternal positions

The comparisons of means of discomfort levels in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test were done by one way ANOVA.

In the supine position, the average discomfort level was 1.25 with standard deviation of 1.15. In the left lateral position, the average discomfort level was 2.06 with standard deviation of 1.08. In the semi-flower position, the average discomfort level was 2.80 with standard deviation of 1.45.

The test statistics value of ANOVA test was 23.25 with p value 0.000. The p value less than 0.05, hence reject the null hypothesis. **That means there is significant difference in discomfort levels in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test.**

Table 5: Comparison of Fetal heart rate in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test n=60

Fetal heart rate - During Test					
Positions	N	Mean	SD	F value	p value
Supine	60	152.97	5.32	27.72	0.000
Left Lateral	60	147.23	3.74		
Semi-Fowler's	60	151.63	4.03		

Figure 2: Comparison of Fetal heart rate in different maternal positions

The comparisons of means of fetal heart rate in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test were done by one way ANOVA.

In the supine position, the average fetal heart rate was 152.97 with standard deviation of 5.32. In the left lateral position, the average fetal heart rate was 147.23 with standard deviation of 3.74. In the semi-flower position, the average fetal heart rate was 151.63 with standard deviation of 4.03.

The test statistics value of ANOVA test was 27.72 with p value 0.000. The p value less than 0.05, hence reject the null hypothesis. **That means there is significant difference in fetal heart rate in different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test.**

SECTION IV

Deals with analysis of data related to association between discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in different maternal positions with their selected demographic variable

ASSOCIATION OF DISCOMFORT LEVELS WITH DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES – SUPINE POSITION **n=60**

Table 6: Association of discomfort levels with demographic variables

Variable	Groups	Discomfort - Supine		Chi Square	d.f.	P value	Significance
		Present	Absent				
Age (in years)	< 20	0	10	6.88	2	0.032	Significant
	21-30	3	38				
	> 30	3	6				
Socioeconomic status	Rs 40000 - 50000	2	22	0.74	2	0.69	Not Significant
	Rs 20000 - 40000	4	28				
	< Rs 20000	0	4				
Patient occupation	Working	1	12	1.90	2	0.39	Not Significant
	Not working	5	31				
	Students	0	11				
	Others	0	0				
Patient Education	10th standard	0	5	4.96	2	0.08	Not Significant
	12 standard	2	36				
	Graduate	4	13				
	Post Graduate	0	0				
Area of residence	Urban	5	30	1.82	2	0.40	Not Significant
	Rural	1	19				
	Slum	0	5				
Obstetrical score	Gravida 1	0	30	7.34	2	0.025	Significant
	Gravida 2	5	17				
	Gravida 3	1	7				
Antenatal visit	One	0	0	1.88	2	0.39	Not Significant
	Two	0	8				
	Three	4	22				
	Four	2	24				

The chi square test was used to see association between discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in supine position with their selected demographic variables.

The test was conducted at 5% level of significance.

Significant Association:

For the demographic variables age and obstetrical score, p value of association test with discomfort levels was less than 0.05. That means, discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in supine position was associated with these demographic variables.

Concludes that, there was significant association of these demographic variables with the discomfort levels.

No Significant Association:

For the demographic variables socioeconomic status, patient's occupation, education etc., p value of association test with discomfort levels was more than 0.05. That means, discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in supine position was not associated with these demographic variables.

Concludes that, there was no significant association of these demographic variables with the discomfort levels.

ASSOCIATION OF DISCOMFORT LEVELS WITH DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES - LEFT LATERAL POSITION

n=60

Table 7: Association of discomfort levels with demographic variables

Variable	Groups	Discomfort - Left Lateral		Chi Square	d.f.	P value	Significance
		Present	Absent				
Age (in years)	< 20	5	5	6.70	2	0.035	Significant
	21-30	18	23				
	> 30	0	9				
Socioeconomic status	Rs 40000 - 50000	13	11	4.25	2	0.12	Not Significant
	Rs 20000 - 40000	9	23				
	< Rs 20000	1	3				
Patient occupation	Working	7	6	7.01	2	0.030	Significant
	Not working	9	27				
	Students	7	4				
	Others	0	0				
Patient Education	10th standard	1	4	1.94	2	0.38	Not Significant
	12 standard	17	21				
	Graduate	5	12				
	Post Graduate	0	0				

Area of residence	Urban	12	23	2.10	2	0.35	Not Significant
	Rural	10	10				
	Slum	1	4				
Obstetrical score	Gravida 1	15	15	4.38	2	0.11	Not Significant
	Gravida 2	7	15				
	Gravida 3	1	7				
Antenatal visit	One	0	0	0.77	2	0.68	Not Significant
	Two	2	6				
	Three	10	16				
	Four	11	15				

ASSOCIATION OF DISCOMFORT LEVELS WITH DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES - LEFT LATERAL POSITION

The chi square test was used to see association between discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in left lateral position with their selected demographic variables.

The test was conducted at 5% level of significance.

Significant Association:

For the demographic variables age and occupation, p value of association test with discomfort levels was less than 0.05. That means, discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in left lateral position was associated with these demographic variables.

Concludes that, there was significant association of these demographic variables with the discomfort levels.

No Significant Association:

For the demographic variables socioeconomic status, education, area of residence etc., p value of association test with discomfort levels was more than 0.05. That means, discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in left lateral position was not associated with these demographic variables.

Concludes that, there was no significant association of these demographic variables with the discomfort levels.

ASSOCIATION OF DISCOMFORT LEVELS WITH DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES - SEMI - FOWLERS POSITION

n=60

Table 8: Association of discomfort levels with demographic variables

Variable	Groups	Discomfort - Semi - Fowler's		Chi Square	d.f.	p value	Significance
		Present	Absent				
Age (in years)	< 20	0	10	1.10	2	0.58	Not Significant
	21-30	4	37				
	> 30	1	8				
Socioeconomic status	Rs 40000 - 50000	2	22	1.63	2	0.44	Not Significant
	Rs 20000 - 40000	2	30				
	< Rs 20000	1	3				
Patient occupation	Working	2	11	1.84	2	0.40	Not Significant
	Not working	3	33				
	Students	0	11				
	Others	0	0				
Patient Education	10th standard	0	5	0.82	2	0.66	Not Significant
	12 standard	4	34				
	Graduate	1	16				
	Post Graduate	0	0				
Area residence of	Urban	3	32	1.18	2	0.55	Not Significant
	Rural	1	19				
	Slum	1	4				
Obstetrical score	Gravida 1	3	27	0.70	2	0.70	Not Significant
	Gravida 2	1	21				
	Gravida 3	1	7				
Antenatal visit	One	0	0	1.09	2	0.58	Not Significant
	Two	0	8				
	Three	2	24				
	Four	3	23				

The chi square test was used to see association between discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in semi-fowlers position with their selected demographic variables.

The test was conducted at 5% level of significance.

No Significant Association:

For all the demographic variables age, socioeconomic status, education etc., p value of association test with discomfort levels was more than 0.05. That means, discomfort levels of fetus and mothers during NST in semi-fowlers position was not associated with these demographic variables.

Concludes that, there was no significant association of these demographic variables with the discomfort levels.

DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non Stress Test (NST) on selected physiological parameters of the mother and fetus. The findings of the study revealed important insights regarding maternal comfort and fetal heart rate in various positions.

Before the NST, there was no statistically significant difference in the physiological parameters of mothers such as systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure , heart rate , oxygen saturation and respiratory rate across the three positions (supine , left lateral and semi fowler's). This indicates that all mothers were physiologically stable before the procedure and that baseline parameters were comparable.

During the NST, significant differences were observed in maternal heart rate, oxygen saturation and respiratory rate. This suggests that maternal position has a measurable effect on maternal physiological responses during the test. The left lateral position showed relatively better oxygen saturation and stable heart rate compared to the supine position. This may be due to reduced compression of the inferior vena cava in the left lateral position, which improves venous return and cardiac output, thereby enhancing maternal and fetal oxygenation.

A highly significant difference was observed in fetal heart rate across the three positions. The lowest fetal heart rate was observed in the left lateral position, indicating better fetal well-being. This finding supports existing literature which states that the left lateral position improves uteroplacental blood flow and prevents supine hypotension syndrome, thereby promoting optimal fetal oxygenation.

Regarding maternal discomfort, significant differences were noted among all three positions. The supine position was associated with the highest level of discomfort, while the left lateral and semi-fowler's positions were comparatively more comfortable. The left lateral position showed the least discomfort during NST. This may be due to reduced pressure on the back and abdomen and better body support.

The association analysis showed that discomfort levels were significantly associated with age and obstetrical score in the supine position, and with age and occupation in the leftl ateral

position. However, no significant association was found between discomfort levels and demographic variables in the semi-fowler's position. This indicates that individual characteristics may influence comfort in certain positions, especially in the supine posture.

Overall, the study findings clearly demonstrate that maternal position during NST plays a significant role in maternal comfort and fetal heart rate. Among the three positions, the left lateral position was found to be the most effective and comfortable, ensuring better maternal physiological stability and improved fetal well-being.

CONCLUSION

This chapter presents the conclusion drawn, implications, limitations, and recommendations. The focus of this study was to assess the effectiveness of different maternal positions during Non-Stress Test on selected physiological parameters of fetus and mothers admitted in antenatal ward of selected hospitals. In this study Quantitative Research, Quasi-experimental, one-group counterbalanced repeated measures design was used 60 samples were selected from hospitals using the purposive sampling technique. The data was collected by questionnaire, data was analyzed and interpreted by applying statistical methods. For generating necessary data, content validation was done by 13 experts from different fields. The data was collected from 12/12/2025 to 13/01/2026. At the start of the data collection, the study was discussed with samples. Samples were selected according to the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. This explained the purpose of the study and assured about confidentiality of the information between the investigator and the respondent. The researcher felt a deep sense of satisfaction and fulfillment at having undertaken the study. The study provided deeper insight and empathy towards the need for expert guidance from the guide and cooperation of teachers has made this study a fruitful and pleasant experience.

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